

The Coupling Constants Series and Bosonic Transformations - 8T

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Abstract:

By analyzing the primorial equation of coupling constants magnitudes of the new 8T, and in particular the equivalence among the first three interactions at $24 + 2$ variations, it is possible to expend the idea to net curvature transformations at high energy. In particular the Gluon and the Photon to possess an exact morphism unto the Bosons of the weak interaction.

Introduction

The 8T setting is a Lorentz manifold, $s = (M, g)$, with (3,1) signature. The manifold is the connected manifold, invoked stationary, $s = s_0 \times \mathbb{R}$. The manifold has areas of extremum curvatures that remain as they are overtime, this are yielding time invariant acceleration from them on the metric tensor M, given by two conditions below (1). The reason for the acceleration in the 8T is that the manifold is a part of an infinite packet of universes, which interact at areas of extremum curvatures, as g is the Ricci flow, and as a result flatten each other metric tensor causing it to accelerate in a time invariant rate, given by equations (1.2) and (1.21). By (1.2) those manifolds are topologically invariant.

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s} \frac{\partial s}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s'} \frac{\partial s'}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g'} \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \cap \frac{\partial^2 g'}{\partial t^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} = 0 \quad (1.1)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_1} \frac{\partial s_1}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{\partial \mathcal{L}}{\partial s_n} \frac{\partial s_n}{\partial M} \frac{\partial M}{\partial g} \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} = 0 \quad (1.2)$$

The manifold experience arbitrary amount of net curvature isomorphic to prime numbers or the number one. That construction yielded the primorial coupling constants series presented in equations (1.4) to (1.43) present the first and second representation. I.e. net curvature on the matric tensor and the prime critical line.

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1.4}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.41}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.42}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1): (24 + (3)) + 3: (120 + (3)) + 5: (840 + (3)) + 7 ... \tag{1.43}$$

$$8 + (1)$$

$$[(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 \rightarrow \left[2N_1 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N_2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

$$[(120 * 7) + (3)] + 7 \rightarrow \left[2N_3 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2}$$

For example, the Electromagnetic coupling term, we have proven the invariant three to be an electron:

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow [(24 * 5) + (e)] + \gamma \quad (1.44)$$

In the 8T thesis we searched for the point of alignment of the first three interactions. The point on alignment Boson wise means that the net variation is the same for all three interactions. According to this axiom we aligned the first three interactions on $N_V = (+3)$, that is by three real exchanges and one virtual. As presented in the 8T thesis.

$$[8 + (1)] + 3 - (\mathbf{1}\nu): \quad [(8 * 3) + (3)] + 3 : \quad [(24 * 5) + (3)] + \mathbf{3} \quad (1.5)$$

The reason we need the virtual exchange of variation on the strong is to allow the term to vanish, eleven variation cannot vanish, but ten, as an even can vanish. Overall we had four exchanges of variation, three real and one virtual. Those exchanges modified the middle coupling term. By demanding the net variation equivalent for all, and the invariant three to stay as it is, the modification effected the left term of the coupling, yielding:

$$((8 * 3) + 2) = 26. \quad (1.51)$$

That is because we took the average amount of exchanges between the two terms, the strong and the electric. Up until now, reader is probability familiar with every equation presented, as those are 8T fundamentals. From here on out, we have a completely new paper. In physical setting, it means that in high energy there is a morphism, and the Boson of the strong as well as the Electromagnetic are transforming onto the Boson of the weak interaction, as for an infinitesimal period of time they are aligned on the $N_V = (+3)$. We can predict that in high energy these processes will happen.

$$\gamma \rightarrow W^+$$

Of course, these could be the other Bosonic particles of the weak interaction. For the third coupling term:

$$[(24 * 5) + (e)] + W^+$$

Notice that the strong interaction will include the Gluon and the Boson of the weak interaction:

$$[8 + (g)] + W^+ - (\mathbf{1}\nu)$$

The W^+ cannot stay as it is, as the series would not make sense, that is why we defined the virtual exchange of variation. Meaning that the W^+ must vanish from the first coupling term. It also means that in high energy, the strong interaction will generate the weak interaction Boson, alongside the strong interacting Gluon. That the discrete amount of prime curvature can deform onto one other.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)